

IPBES BBA Chapter 2 – Figures 2.2, 2.6, 2.8 and Table 2.5 / IPBES business and biodiversity assessment (2.2)

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1. Description

This data management report accompanies the methodological assessment of the impact and dependence of business on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people for Chapter 2: *How does business depend on biodiversity?* The purpose of this report is to ensure transparency and traceability of the data handling and analytical steps that underlie the figures and tables presented in the chapter. Specifically, it documents the processes followed by experts to produce figures 2.2, 2.6, 2.8 and table 2.5. Each section describes the procedures applied to compile, classify, and analyse the data used. All data were prepared by the authors to illustrate dependencies on nature's contributions to people, as discussed in Chapter 2.

2. Figure 2.2 Economic benefits of pollination services in USD dollars for different crops and International Standard Industrial Classification subcategories in Brazil.

This Sankey figure shows the economic benefits of pollination services in Brazil (USD) for different crops grouped into their corresponding International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC) subcategories. Using data from Giannini et al. (2015) (additional file A), experts extracted the economic value of pollination service (left column on figure 2.2. Chapter 2) and grouped individual crops into broader ISIC subcategories (middle column on figure 2.2.). For example, beans, broad beans, and cowpeas (left column) are classified under "legumes" (middle column). The thickness of the grey lines represents the magnitude of the economic benefits of pollination services for Brazil.

3. Figure 2.6 Flows between ecosystem services and economic sectors in the European Union.

This Sankey figure shows flows between ecosystem services and economic sectors for the European Union in 2018, using the Monetary Use accounts downloaded from the INCA Platform (Joint Research Centre, European Commission, n.d.) accounting tables; data accessed in February 2024 (additional file B). For the EU aggregate, experts extracted the 2018 monetary use value for each ecosystem service with their corresponding economic sector pair and linked those values using a Sankey diagram (no additional processing was done). The ecosystem services included were water purification; carbon sequestration; pollination; crop provision; flood control; habitat and species maintenance; recreation; soil retention, and wood provision. These are linked to the sectors agriculture, industry, services, households, and forestry. Where the INCA data does not allocate a value to a sector, experts used a "Not linked to a specific sector" node. For example, carbon sequestration is not linked to a specific economic sector. Note that the INCA team has since revised how results are presented and modelled; both the set of ecosystem services and the values (e.g., crop pollination for 2018) may differ in later releases of the platform.

4. Figure 2.8 Comparison of ecosystem service dependencies of the national economies of Brazil and Kenya.

These two bars stacked figures compare ecosystem service dependencies in the national economies of Brazil and Kenya, combining the REX 3 multi-regional input output (MRIO) database with the ENCORE database (ENCORE, 2024) (additional file C). Bars indicate the number of instances in which an ecosystem service is rated as a "High" or "Very High" dependency for an economic activity.

To produce this figure, experts mapped economic activities in REX 3 to ENCORE classifications, which provide dependency ratings for 25 ecosystem services across 271 economic activities. Only activities rated “High” or “Very High” were retained. National production vectors were then propagated through supply chains using the MRIO framework to capture indirect dependencies tier by tier; values converged by Tier 4. For each tier, experts summed the counts of “High/Very High” dependencies by ecosystem service and visualized the results as stacked bar charts, distinguishing direct from indirect (Tiers 1–4) contributions. The REX 3 MRIO (2023 release) supplied national production and inter-industry linkages for Brazil and Kenya, while ENCORE (2024) supplied ecosystem service dependency ratings used to classify “High” and “Very High” dependencies.

5. Table 2.5 Summary of central bank studies on business dependencies on nature’s contributions to people.

An internet search, supplemented by targeted screening of publications from the Network for Greening the Financial System (NGFS) and the snowballing approach used in Chapter 2, identified studies that (i) assess business–nature dependencies on ecosystem services and (ii) are authored by central banks or analyze central-bank data. The review occurred in July 2024. For each included study, the most important ecosystem services were recorded using the ENCORE framework (Exploring Natural Capital Opportunities, Risks and Exposure), along with the most important sectors, the type of financial portfolio assessed, and the share of the portfolio dependent on at least one ecosystem service; when values appeared only in graphics, they were digitized with WebPlotDigitizer.

Because the included studies relied on a pre–June 2024 ENCORE release that referenced sector taxonomies other than the target classification, sector results reported in GICS (Global Industry Classification Standard) or NACE (Nomenclature statistique des activités économiques dans la Communauté européenne) were harmonized to ISIC (International Standard Industrial Classification) using the closest available detailed crosswalk. Results are shown in Table 2.5, which summarizes central-bank studies on business dependencies on nature’s contributions to people: numbers denote available rankings from 1 (highest, darker) to 5 (lowest, lighter). Note: ENCORE rates ecosystem-service dependencies on a five-point scale—very low, low, medium, high, very high (ENCORE, n.d.); the table reports only (very) high dependencies.

6. References

- Giannini, T. C., Cordeiro, G. D., Freitas, B. M., Saraiva, A. M., & Imperatriz-Fonseca, V. L. (2015). The Dependence of Crops for Pollinators and the Economic Value of Pollination in Brazil. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 108(3), 849–857. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jee/tov093>
- Joint Research Centre, European Commission. (n.d.). *Integrated Natural Capital Accounting (INCA) Platform*. <https://ecosystem-accounts.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>
- Global Canopy, UNEP Finance Initiative, & UNEP-WCMC. (2024). ENCORE (Exploring Natural Capital Opportunities, Risks and Exposure) knowledge base [version 2024 update]. ENCORE. <https://encorenature.org/en/data-and-methodology>
- Cabernard, L., Pfister, S., & Hellweg, S. (2023). Resolved Exiobase version 3 (REX3) [data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8098722> zenodo.org

7. Additional files

ID	Name	File Type	Size (KB)	Description
A	IPBES_BBA_2.2_09-2025(A)	.XLS	161	Data used for figure 2.2
B	IPBES_BBA_2.2_09-2025 (B)	.XLS	144	Data used for figure 2.6
C	IPBES_BBA_2.2_09-2025 (C)	.XLS	32,1	Data used for figure 2.8